

Meta-Learning-Based Service-Aware User Associations: An ORIGAMI Approach

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Abstract—Future 6G networks are expected to support highly heterogeneous and latency-critical services over dynamic radio and compute infrastructures spanning the edge-to-cloud continuum. In this setting, user association can no longer be treated as a purely radio-centric problem, as end-to-end performance depends jointly on radio access conditions and service-specific latency, both of which may vary rapidly over time. Based on the architecture of the EU-funded project ORIGAMI and its Dynamic Fairness and Load Balancing (FLB) use case, this paper studies a service-aware user association problem under non-stationary conditions, where a controller assigns each user to a serving cell while keeping the application-dependent (from transportation, processing, etc) and potential handover (if there is a change in association decisions) delays to a minimum. Importantly, these latencies are not only unknown at the time the user associations are determined but are also assumed to be time-varying and even chosen by an adversary aiming to disrupt the user’s quality of experience/service. To solve this problem and address these challenges, we propose a framework based on online meta-learning that combines the decisions of multiple learners (or algorithms, experts), each with different learning rates (as the problem is difficult to tackle) via a meta-learning algorithm that tracks and chooses the best performing one(s) for the experienced conditions. Finally, we establish a theoretical dynamic regret guarantee against a powerful benchmark (i.e., oracle) and validate the approach using real-world data from a top-tier mobile network operator in Europe.

Index Terms—ORIGAMI Architecture, Online Meta-Learning, User Associations, Handovers, Latency Minimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation

The impending 6G era promises to support unprecedented services such as holographic communications, tactile internet, autonomous driving, and massive digital twinning, driving stringent requirements for ultra-low latency, extremely high reliability, and massive resource and storage availability [1], [2]. To meet these demanding Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) affordably and sustainably, the architecture of current mobile systems must evolve rapidly. The EU-funded project *ORIGAMI*¹ aims to break down existing barriers in mobile architecture through three fundamental innovations: a Global Service-Based Architecture (GSBA), a Compute Continuum Layer (CCL), and a Zero-Trust Exposure Layer (ZTL).

A critical challenge in this heterogeneous 6G landscape, characterized by diverse access points (APs) and distributed

Fig. 1. The proposed Meta-Learning-based service-aware user association NI executing within the ORIGAMI architecture. The solution resides in the CCL as an xApp, utilizing the GSBA bus to gather real-time RAN/Edge metrics and enforce dynamic association decisions to address ORIGAMI’s FLB objectives.

computing resources spanning the edge-to-cloud continuum, is the optimal management of service-aware user associations. The traditional problem of user association, namely, assigning each user to a serving cell, has evolved into a complex “user-service” association challenge. Different services required by each user may be optimally served by different compute locations accessed via different links. Furthermore, the 6G environment is highly dynamic and “non-stationary,” where changes in users’ serving cell, known as *handovers* (HOs), and rapidly changing service demands render static optimization methods obsolete.

This dynamicity presents a significant obstacle, identified by ORIGAMI as *Barrier #3: “High latency to process complex 6G network problems”* [3]. In this work, we address this barrier by developing a novel Network Intelligence (NI) solution within the ORIGAMI framework (Fig. 1). We instantiate the *Dynamic Fairness and Load Balancing (FLB)* ORIGAMI use case [3], specifically adapted for the radio domain. Unlike traditional approaches that react sluggishly to changes or require expensive retraining, our solution leverages *online convex optimization (OCO)* [4], and more precisely, the recent advances in smoothed online learning (SOL) [5]. A *meta-learning* framework is proposed that dynamically selects and combines association policies from a pool of *experts* (i.e., algorithms or learners), each tailored for different conditions. The necessity of the meta-learning layer compared to sim-

¹<https://sns-origami.eu/>

pler adaptive online optimization baselines lies in the non-stationarity of the operating conditions (e.g., mobility patterns, service delays, etc), which are unknown a priori and evolve over time. To address this, we maintain a sufficiently rich family of experts with different learning rates, ensuring that at least one expert is superior to the yet-to-be-seen conditions. The proposed algorithm provides theoretical guarantees in terms of *expected dynamic regret*, a rigorous measure of how well the algorithm performs compared to an omniscient *oracle*, under a vast range of scenarios for the changing parameters.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, our proposed solution operates as an NI xApp [6] deployed within ORIGAMI’s CCL, utilizing the extended GSBA bus to ingest real-time metrics (such as link latency, compute load, and channel quality) from the radio access network (RAN) and Edge domains. The resulting association decisions chosen by the meta-learner are then enforced back down to the infrastructure via the GSBA.

B. Related Work

Previous works in (deep) Reinforcement Learning (RL/DRL) approaches have studied the user association problem [7], [8] and handovers in general [9]. While powerful, RL often suffers from high training latency, lack of robust convergence guarantees, “catastrophic forgetting” when faced with rapidly shifting network environments, and the curse of dimensionality [10], failing to provide the real-time responsiveness required for critical 6G services.

Recent field measurements [11] and real-world data from MNOs [12] in commercial 5G networks demonstrate that HO delay remains substantial and highly variable across architectures, UEs, cells, and configurations, motivating the importance of incorporating this element to the user association problem. Moreover, several works have shown that end-to-end latency in mobile systems depends on services/applications apart from radio access, and that mobility further complicates its analysis [13], [14]. Although these works motivate service-aware control, they rely on explicit service placement or known models, whereas we focus on online user association under non-stationary conditions, which are not observed (and can even be adversarial) before making a decision.

Meta-learning is finding increasing applications in communication systems due to its robustness to distribution shifts and fast-adaptation [15]. We refer, e.g., to [16] for load balancing, [17] for handovers in vehicle-to-network communications, and [18], [19] for conditional handovers [20] optimization. With respect to prior meta-learning and smoothed OCO approaches and closer to our setting, the authors of [21] proposed a meta-learning framework for user associations that explicitly accounts for HO delays and adapts to non-stationary environments. While [21] moves toward a more realistic operational model by avoiding offline training and leveraging meta-learning, its objective is to maximize users’ throughput rather than to minimize end-to-end delay (current work). Moreover, in this work, we account for service- or application-dependent latency components that arise beyond the RAN, which is fundamentally new beyond existing techniques.

Fig. 2. Illustrative four-layer network structure: a controller assigns users to cells in a service-aware manner. Each user runs a specific service, while cell-service connectivity captures the aggregate latency of the corresponding application, abstracting away individual server instances.

C. Contributions

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- We formulate the service-aware user association problem in 6G as a learning problem, with the goal of minimizing the total delay experienced by users. To tackle it, we propose an online meta-learning-based NI solution that adapts to any mobility and delay regimes without prior knowledge of these dynamics and aligns with the ORIGAMI FLB use case.
- We provide theoretical dynamic regret guarantees for the performance of the proposed algorithm against a powerful oracle that has full knowledge of the system conditions (basically, delays), which can even change adversarially. In this way, we satisfy key Non-Functional Requirements (NFRs) of the ORIGAMI project architecture.
- We evaluate our algorithm with real-world data captured from a top-tier Mobile Network Operator (MNO) in Europe.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Sec. II introduces the system model, which includes the main components of the analysis and defines the associated delays. Sec. III introduces the objective function that we aim to minimize and discusses the difficulty in tackling this problem. Sec. IV presents the proposed solution and performance guarantees, while Sec. V evaluates this solution under real-world conditions. Our study concludes in Sec. VI.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Main Components

We consider a heterogeneous cellular network, consisting of four main components: (i) a set \mathcal{I} of UEs, with $|\mathcal{I}| = I$, (ii) a set \mathcal{J} of cells/base stations, with $|\mathcal{J}| = J$, (iii) a set \mathcal{M} of service classes/applications (video, gaming, chat, etc), with $|\mathcal{M}| = M$, and (iv) a controller (e.g., near-RT RIC xApp) operating in a time-slotted manner; namely, in slots $t \in \mathcal{T} = \{1, \dots, T\}$ with near-RT granularity (hundreds of ms). Each user $i \in \mathcal{I}$ is associated with exactly one service $m \in \mathcal{M}$; we denote by $\mathcal{I}_m \subseteq \mathcal{I}$ the set of users running service m . An overview of this structure can be viewed in Fig. 2.

The goal of the controller is to assign/associate users to cells while minimizing the *total delay* (as defined in the next subsection) experienced by the users. Specifically, we define the (discrete) decision of the controller as:

$$x_{ij}(t) \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (1)$$

where $x_{ij}(t) = 1$ indicates that user i is served by cell j in slot t ; and $x_{ij}(t) = 0$ otherwise.

It is assumed that each user i is served by one cell in each slot, namely, $\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} x_{ij}(t) = 1$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, t \in \mathcal{T}$, while each cell $j \in \mathcal{J}$ has a capacity constraint C_j (e.g., max number of concurrently served UEs in the scheduling slot), namely, $\ell_j(t) \triangleq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} x_{ij}(t) \leq C_j$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}, t \in \mathcal{T}$.

For each service class $m \in \mathcal{M}$, cells may be connected to one or more backend servers implementing it; the selection of a specific server instance is handled outside the controller.

B. Delay Model

The delay that the controller needs to minimize can be defined at each slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$ as:

$$d_{ij}(t) = d_{ij}^R(t) + d_{jm_i}^S(t) \quad (2)$$

where $d_{ij}^R(t)$ is the radio access (i.e., *user-to-cell*) delay when user i is served by cell j in slot t and $d_{jm}^S(t)$ is the *cell-to-service* latency experienced by traffic of service m when served by cell j due to, e.g., transportation, processing, and queueing effects, as can be seen in Fig. 2. Since each user i is associated with a (fixed) service class m_i , the delay experienced at cell j is given by evaluating this quantity at $m = m_i$. For presentation purposes, we aggregate all delay elements in a single component $\mathbf{d}_t = (d_{ij}(t), i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J})$.

More precisely, let $r_{ij}(t)$ be the achievable rate (i.e., *throughput*) from cell j to user i in slot t . We consider a standard mapping from SINR to rate [7], [21], namely, $r_{ij}(t) = W_j \log(1 + \text{SINR}_{ij}(t))$, where W_j is the portion of the bandwidth/spectrum that cell j is allowed to give to each UE. Let $b_i(t)$ be the number of arriving bits in the slot (or a representative packet size). Thus, the total user-to-cell delay is $d_{ij}^R(t) = b_i(t)/(r_{ij}(t) + \epsilon)$: with $\epsilon > 0$ preventing instability when rates are zero. This captures the monotone decrease of delay with SINR and rate.

As far as the cell-to-service delay $d_{jm}^S(t)$ is concerned, we do not impose any specific functional form. Instead, we treat it as a general, time-varying quantity that captures the aggregate transport, processing, and queueing latency experienced by traffic of service m when served by cell j . This delay may reflect the minimum latency among multiple backend server instances implementing service m and is observable via, e.g., RTT probes and gNB-to-edge counters.

Importantly, both delay terms, namely $d_{ij}^R(t)$ and $d_{jm}^S(t)$, are allowed to be non-stationary and are revealed to the controller only after the association decision in eq. (1) is applied to the system, as it becomes obvious in the subsequent section.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION: ONLINE DELAY MINIMIZATION WITH SWITCHING COSTS

A. Objective

In our framework, we introduce the *loss* function that the controller needs to minimize as follows:

$$f_t(\mathbf{x}_t) = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_m} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} x_{ij}(t) \log(d_{ij}^R(t) + d_{jm}^S(t)), \quad (3)$$

with $\mathbf{x}_t = (x_{ij}(t) \in \{0, 1\}, i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J})$ being the user association/assignment decision of the controller in slot $t \in \mathcal{T}$. The logarithm is used to ensure fairness, avoiding a small subset of users/services from suffering large delays [7], [21]; however, we highlight that other functions can be used (e.g., without the log), based on the desired behavior.

The goal of the controller is not only to minimize the loss function of eq. (3), but also to penalize frequent changes in association decisions. In other words, association-decision changes (i.e., transferring active sessions from one cell to another) in consecutive slots, namely $x_{ij}(t) \neq x_{ij}(t-1)$, lead to *handovers* (HOs), which often cause increased delays and failures, especially in dense deployments and heterogeneous radio access technologies [12], [22]. We capture these changes using the norm $\|\mathbf{x}_t - \mathbf{x}_{t-1}\|$, as in [7], [21].

Nevertheless, the objective of the controller is not merely to decrease the switches/HOs (as they are deemed necessary for, e.g., moving users), but to minimize the *HO delay*, which can be different for each user-cell pair. For instance, 2G/3G cells are more prone to HO failures [12], and thus, HOs to these cells should be penalized more than intra-frequency 4G/5G HOs. This idea is captured through the weighted norm $\|\mathbf{x}_t - \mathbf{x}_{t-1}\|_{\mathbf{A}_t}$, where $\mathbf{A}_t = \text{diag}(a_n(t) > 0)$ is a positive definite matrix with its diagonal weights/penalties $a_n(t) \in [0, 1]$, $n = 1, \dots, I \cdot J$ for different user-cell pairs, which may even change over time (e.g., higher for inter-frequency or inter-vendor transitions, or for latency-sensitive services). Generally, $\|u\|_{\mathbf{A}_t} = \sqrt{u^\top \mathbf{A}_t u}$ [23].

All in all, the loss function, together with the *switching cost/delay* introduced from potential HOs, lead to the objective function that the controller wishes to minimize:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}: \min_{\{\mathbf{x}_t\}_{t=1}^T} & \sum_{t=1}^T \left(f_t(\mathbf{x}_t) + \|\mathbf{x}_t - \mathbf{x}_{t-1}\|_{\mathbf{A}_t} \right) \\ \text{s.t. } & \mathbf{x}_t \in \{0, 1\}^{I \cdot J}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \\ & \ell_j(t) \leq C_j, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, j \in \mathcal{J}. \end{aligned}$$

B. Why Learning is Necessary

Problem \mathbb{P} is not amenable to offline optimization because key terms are unknown at the beginning of the slots and/or time-varying. Specifically:

- *Non-stationary radio/signal measurements.* $\text{SINR}_{ij}(t)$ varies with mobility, interference, and scheduling; even with reporting, measurements can be stale at decision time.
- *Delay observation.* $d_{ij}(t)$ is accurately observed only after association decisions are applied; congestion and workload shifts might create abrupt changes.
- *Memory.* Switching costs introduce memory effects, as past decisions influence current decisions.
- *Discrete decisions.* Discreteness of \mathbf{x}_t prevents the application of off-the-shelf online convex optimization techniques.

Despite these challenges, the goal is to design an online learning algorithm that determines UE-cell associations, minimizes the total delay, and is oblivious to all time-varying and unknown *system conditions*, including future system and HO delays for each UE-cell pair.

IV. META-LEARNING ALGORITHM

As analyzed in the previous section, the discreteness of \mathbf{x}_t prevents the direct application of online convex optimization techniques. To overcome this and solve the problem at hand, we take the following steps:

- 1) Relax the discreteness of the decision variable \mathbf{x}_t to a continuous one, transforming the problem to a convex one.
- 2) Solve the convex problem.
- 3) Map the obtained continuous solution back to the discrete (i.e., implementable) domain via careful rounding.

A. Convex Relaxation

By defining $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}, t \in \mathcal{T}$:

$$x_{ij}^c(t) \in [0, 1], \quad \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} x_{ij}^c(t) = 1, \quad \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} x_{ij}^c(t) \leq C_j, \quad (4)$$

the per-slot loss in (3) is linear in $x_{ij}^c(t)$, and hence, convex.

We assume that at the end of slot t , the controller obtains the radio-derived delays $d_{ij}^R(t)$ for relevant (i, j) pairs (from SINR/rate reports), and the cell-to-server delays $d_{jm}^S(t)$ through, e.g., RTT probes and gNB-to-edge counters.

B. Meta-Learner (Hedge) and Experts (OGD)

To approach \mathbb{P} , we employ a pool-of-experts scheme in which each expert runs online gradient descent (OGD) [24] on the relaxed/continuous domain, and a meta-learner [25], [26] combines experts' decisions using Hedge [27]. The intuition behind this algorithmic choice lies in the non-stationarity of the environment/conditions. Specifically, since the mobility patterns or services that the UEs access, as well as the associated delays, are not known a priori, we consider a sufficiently rich set of experts with different learning rates. With an appropriate choice of rates, this guarantees that at least one expert performs well for the realized operating conditions. We identify and track the best-performing expert online via a meta-learning mechanism based on the Hedge algorithm, which assigns and dynamically updates weights to the experts' decisions according to their observed performance.

Formally, let \mathcal{K} be the set of experts, with $|\mathcal{K}| = K$. Each expert $k \in \mathcal{K}$ proposes a decision $\mathbf{x}_t^k = (x_{ij}^k(t) \in \{0, 1\}, i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J})$ and uses a learning rate/step θ_k . The meta-learner maintains weights $\mathbf{w}_t \in \Delta_K$, where Δ_K is a K -dimensional probability simplex, and forms:

$$\mathbf{x}_t^m = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} w_t^k \mathbf{x}_t^k. \quad (5)$$

Since now \mathbf{x}_t^m takes continuous values (as in eq. (4)), the controller samples a discrete assignment \mathbf{x}_t using any unbiased estimator for which it holds that $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}_t] = \mathbf{x}_t^m$. This can be achieved by deciding/sampling the serving cell j for each user i using the row's i probabilities from \mathbf{x}_t^m [21].

After observing the delays \mathbf{d}_t and switching costs \mathbf{A}_t , the meta-learner evaluates each expert using a surrogate loss:

$$l_t(\mathbf{x}_t^k) = \langle \nabla f_t(\mathbf{x}_t), \mathbf{x}_t^k - \mathbf{x}_t \rangle + \|\mathbf{x}_t^k - \mathbf{x}_{t-1}^k\|_{\mathbf{A}_t}, \quad (6)$$

Algorithm 1: Meta-Learning Delay-Aware Association (MELDA)

- Require:** Meta step η , expert steps $\{\theta_k\}_{k=1}^K$.
- 1: Sort $\theta_1 \leq \theta_2 \leq \dots \leq \theta_K$ and set $w_1^k = \frac{1+1/K}{k(k+1)}$.
 - 2: **for** $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ **do**
 - 3: Experts propose $\{\mathbf{x}_t^k\}_{k=1}^K$
 - 4: Meta-learner combines decisions in \mathbf{x}_t^m using eq. (5)
 - 5: Take the discrete \mathbf{x}_t by sampling with $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}_t] = \mathbf{x}_t^m$
 - 6: Apply \mathbf{x}_t ; observe delays and \mathbf{A}_t
 - 7: Update weights via eqs. (6)–(7)
 - 8: Experts update via eq. (8)
 - 9: **end for**
-

and updates weights using its learning rate η (defined later):

$$w_{t+1}^k = \frac{w_t^k \exp(-\eta l_t(\mathbf{x}_t^k))}{\sum_{h \in \mathcal{K}} w_t^h \exp(-\eta l_t(\mathbf{x}_t^h))}. \quad (7)$$

Finally, each expert performs a projected gradient step on the feasible set:

$$\mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k = \Pi\left(\mathbf{x}_t^k - \theta_k \nabla f_t(\mathbf{x}_t)\right). \quad (8)$$

A summary of these steps can be seen in Algorithm 1 (MELDA).

C. Performance Analysis

We evaluate the performance of MELDA by comparing it against a powerful benchmark (oracle) that has full a priori knowledge of the *conditions*, namely $\{\mathbf{d}_t, \mathbf{A}_t\}_{t=1}^T$, and can select the optimal sequence of decisions over the entire time horizon. This benchmark is highly competitive, surpassing both static (single best solution for all time slots) and dynamic ones (best solution for each time slot independently) [4], [28].

We adopt the notion of *expected dynamic regret* [5] to quantify performance:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{R}_T] &\triangleq \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E} \left[f_t(\mathbf{x}_t) + \|\mathbf{x}_t - \mathbf{x}_{t-1}\|_{\mathbf{A}_t} \right] \\ &\quad - \sum_{t=1}^T \left(f_t(\mathbf{x}_t^*) + \|\mathbf{x}_t^* - \mathbf{x}_{t-1}^*\|_{\mathbf{A}_t} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\{\mathbf{x}_t^*\}_{t=1}^T$ denotes the oracle sequence, and the expectation is taken with respect to the algorithm's internal randomization induced by discretization. Our objective is to design an online policy such that $\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{R}_T]/T = 0$ for any admissible oracle sequence.

A central quantity in this expected dynamic regret analysis is the *path length* of the oracle, namely, $P_T \triangleq \sum_{t=1}^T \|\mathbf{x}_t^* - \mathbf{x}_{t-1}^*\|_{\mathbf{A}_t}$, which captures the temporal variability of the optimal decisions due to the non-stationarity of the conditions. Intuitively, we employ the meta-learning strategy with a pool of experts with heterogeneous learning rates (each tailored to a different level of conditions' volatility) exactly because P_T is unknown a priori.

Under standard boundedness assumptions on the feasible domain and per-slot delay gradients, the following result characterizes the performance of the proposed algorithm.

Lemma 1 (Expected Dynamic Regret Bound). *There exists a set of $K = \mathcal{O}(\log T)$ experts with heterogeneous learning rates $\{\theta_k\}_{k=1}^K$, chosen on a geometric grid such that*

$$\theta_k = \Theta\left(2^{k-1}T^{-1/2}\right), \quad k = 1, \dots, K, \quad (10)$$

and a meta-learning rate η used in the Hedge update satisfying

$$\eta = \Theta\left(T^{-1/2}\right), \quad (11)$$

for which the following bound holds:

$$\mathbb{E}[R_T] \leq \underbrace{\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{T})}_{\text{OCO term}} + \underbrace{\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{TP_T})}_{\text{path-length adaptivity}} + \underbrace{\text{rounding error}}_{\text{from sampling}}. \quad (12)$$

Proof (Sketch). The proof follows by tailoring the main results of [5], [21], [29]. Due to limited space, we provide the following brief but sufficient explanation. We start from the continuous domain, where the decision changes, together with the gradients of the loss function, are bounded. Since the problem’s variability P_T is unknown a priori, we instantiate a logarithmic number of experts with geometrically spaced learning rates and aggregate them using Hedge, guaranteeing that at least one expert attains the near-optimal regret up to constants. Finally, implementable decisions are obtained by discretizing (through sampling) the relaxed ones; as in the prior works on quantized/rounded online control, this introduces a bounded per-slot gap. Combining these arguments yields the stated expected dynamic regret bound. \square

Lemma 1 establishes that the proposed algorithm achieves sublinear dynamic regret with respect to the relaxed problem, while the discretization required for implementable association decisions induces an unavoidable additive error. As demonstrated empirically in Section V, this error remains small in practical scenarios, and the algorithm closely tracks the oracle performance despite non-stationary system conditions.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

We evaluate the proposed algorithm, MELDA, against several benchmarks, including two RL baselines. More precisely, we consider the (i) Oracle, defined in eq. (9) and computes the optimal association at each slot with full knowledge of the conditions and parameters, (ii) SPREV, a heuristic that assigns each user to the cell providing the highest signal conditions in the previous slot, allowing us to assess whether past conditions suffice, (iii) RAND, a baseline that makes the associations randomly, serving as a minimal benchmark, (iv) DQN, a value-based method with Deep Q-Network [8], and (v) PPO, an actor-critic method with proximal updates through Proximal Policy Optimization [9].

All algorithms are evaluated for $T = 1,000$ slots using real SINR traces consisting of 73,303 signal measurements collected at one-second granularity in an urban area with $J = 100$ cells (20 cell sites). According to previous works [21], we simulate $I = 100$ fast-moving users with velocities uniformly drawn in the range [20-28] m/s and variances in [0, 5] m/s. Additionally, we assume $M = 3$ service classes corresponding

Fig. 3. Comparison of our proposed algorithm MELDA with other benchmarks (right of the blue dashed line) and the oracle (left of the blue dashed line) for $T = 1,000$, $I = 100$, and $J = 20$, across metrics: total loss f (top), switching costs (middle), and episodes to reach the total loss (bottom).

to representative applications: video, gaming, and chat. Each user i is associated with a fixed service class m_i , drawn according to the distribution $\mathbb{P}(m_i = \text{video, gaming, chat}) = (0.5, 0.3, 0.2)$, introducing heterogeneous delays, as described in the sequel. Without loss of generality, we select bandwidths $W_j = 5, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}$, and to ensure that user-to-cell and cell-to-service delays contribute similarly and in accordance with the corresponding service classes, namely, video, gaming and chat, we draw $b_i(t)$ from $\mathcal{U}(30, 50)$, $\mathcal{U}(10, 20)$, $\mathcal{U}(3, 8)$ and $d_{j m_i}^S(t)$ from $\mathcal{U}(0.8, 1.2)$, $\mathcal{U}(0.3, 0.6)$, $\mathcal{U}(0.1, 0.3)$, respectively, where \mathcal{U} is the uniform distribution.²

DQN consists of two hidden layers with 128 neurons and ReLU activations. Exploration follows an ϵ -greedy strategy with $\epsilon_{\text{start}} = 1.0$, $\epsilon_{\text{end}} = 0.05$, and exponential decay constant 200. A replay buffer of size 50k and minibatch size 64 are used, with soft target-network updates ($\tau = 0.01$) to improve stability. The loss is the mean-squared temporal-difference error, optimized with Adam at a learning rate of 10^{-3} . In PPO, the actor and critic share a two-layer MLP backbone (128 neurons per layer, Tanh activations). The actor outputs a categorical distribution over all actions, while the critic outputs a scalar state-value estimate. Training uses generalized advantage estimation with $\lambda = 0.95$, clipped objective parameter $\epsilon = 0.2$, and minibatches of 64 samples for 3 epochs per cycles. Both networks are optimized using Adam with rate 3×10^{-4} .

We highlight that MELDA learns and adapts on-the-fly with a single exposure to the conditions, while these RL methods are trained over hundreds of simulated episodes, having access to the same system dynamics. However, even in this case, Fig. 3 shows that in real-world SINR conditions, MELDA requires a single pass (i.e., episode) to attain a total (normalised, for all slots) loss of 71.04, while DQN, and PPO incur 54.5% and 42.6% higher total loss, respectively, by running each for 500 episodes. Moreover, these two RL algorithms attain $\times 3.7$

²This parameterization is not intended to model specific units (e.g., bits), but rather to create a numerically well-conditioned problem where scales align.

Fig. 4. Average dynamic regret \mathcal{R}_T/T for the second-best performing algorithm according to Fig. 3, SPREV, and the proposed algorithm, MELDA.

higher switching costs than our proposed algorithm, showing that not only their decisions change more often, but also fail to achieve smaller loss. As expected, RAND performs poorly, but with a total loss exceeding that of the best RL benchmark (i.e., PPO) by a mere 15.77% (117.28 vs. 101.3). This shows that even more episodes would be needed for the RL benchmarks.

As far as the best benchmark, SPREV, is concerned (except ORACLE), it achieves only 5.1% higher loss than MELDA, but with a switching cost that is $\times 2.6$ higher. To analyze more deeply the difference between ORACLE and MELDA / SPREV, we show the average dynamic regret of both in Fig. 4. It can be observed that, as Lemma 1 proves, the regret converges towards zero, and specifically, at $t = 1,000$ slot, MELDA attains 50.3% less regret than SPREV.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper addresses the problem of user association in future 6G networks, where the users' quality of service/experience is jointly determined by radio access delays/conditions and application/service-dependent latencies. Motivated by the architecture of the EU-funded project ORIGAMI, and its Dynamic Fairness and Load Balancing (FLB) use case, we consider a setting where the environment might range from stationary/static to even non-stationary, leading to its parameters (e.g., delays, throughput, loads, etc) being unknown when the user association decisions are determined. The problem is further complicated by handover (HO) delays, which arise when association decisions change between slots, and can vary due to external reasons as well.

To cope with these challenges, we propose an online meta-learning framework that combines multiple learners with heterogeneous learning rates through a meta-learning mechanism that adaptively selects the most suitable one(s), because the system's parameters (e.g., delays) might change abruptly (even adversarially). We establish theoretical dynamic regret guarantees with respect to a powerful oracle that has full knowledge of the system evolution, and demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach using real-world data from a top-tier mobile network operator (MNO) in Europe. The results indicate that meta-learning-based online control can provide robust and responsive decision-making for service-oriented 6G architectures, like that of ORIGAMI. Future work includes exploring joint optimization across changing services and different control timescales within the architecture.

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